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THE IMPROVEMENT OF THE PROMOTION OF SYSTEM OF TAX CULTURE

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ANNOTATION

In this article, it is justified that issues of promotion of the tax culture in the system of tax relations are becoming more and more global and serious. The theoretical aspects of ensuring compliance with tax discipline by increasing the tax culture among tax entities, legal regulation of issues related to the development of new effective mechanisms of the relationships that arise between them have been researched.

Keywords: taxpayer, tax discipline, tax culture, tax administration, tax system, budget, obligation, types of taxes, tax concept, mandatory payments.

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SOLIQ MADANIYATI TIZIMINI TARG'IB QILISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada soliq munosabatlari tizimida soliq madaniyatini yuksaltirish masalalari global va jiddiy tus olayotganligi asoslab berilgan. Soliq subyektlarining soliq madaniyatini yuksaltirish orqali soliq intizomiga rioya etilishini ta'minlash, ular o'rtasida yuzaga keladigan munosabatlarning yangi samarali mexanizmlarini ishlab chiqish bilan bog'liq masalalarni huquqiy tartibga solishning nazariy jihatlarini o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: soliq to'lovchi, soliq intizomi, soliq madaniyati, soliq ma'muriyati, soliq tizimi, byudjet, majburiyat, soliq turlari, soliq tushunchasi, majburiy to'lovlar.

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СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ПОПУЛЯРИЗАЦИИ СИСТЕМЫ НАЛОГОВОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье обосновывается, что вопросы продвижения налоговой культуры в системе налоговых отношений становятся все более глобальными и серьезными. Исследованы теоретические аспекты обеспечения соблюдения налоговой дисциплины путем повышения налоговой культуры у налоговых субъектов, правового регулирования вопросов, связанных с выработкой новых эффективных механизмов взаимоотношений, возникающих между ними.

Ключевые слова: налогоплательщик, налоговая дисциплина, налоговая культура, налоговое администрирование, налоговая система, бюджет, обязанность, виды налогов, налоговая концепция, обязательные платежи.

Since the essence, purpose, form and conditions of tax policy are of interest to every citizen, training them in tax literacy and legislation from a young age is one of the best and most effective methods of tax promotion.

Tax discipline is of particular importance in raising taxpayers' tax legal intellectual capacity. It should be noted that only as long as taxpayers become accustomed to the principle of voluntary payment of taxes and fees, the payment of taxes and fees will increase significantly.

In general, tax discipline of citizens is considered to be an important element of tax culture and one of the most important indicators showing the literacy rate of the population.

The most important element of the tax culture is the tax discipline, which is the moral and ethical behavior of the taxpayer to calculate the budgets, taking into account the various situations of the mutual relations of the tax authorities on the payment of taxes and the acceptance and processing of tax obligations, is the regular training, development and control of financial skills and capabilities.

Tax discipline is a distinctive part of tax culture and shows citizens' response to obligations to pay taxes and fees to the budget established by law.

In our opinion, tax discipline can be understood as the complex implementation of tax legislation by tax-paying physical and legal entities.

The term "tax culture" is often considered in science together with the concept of "tax literacy"; moreover, these concepts are often confused. In fact, culture and literacy are interrelated in any sphere, including tax relations, and literacy is a necessary condition for the formation and development of culture, its necessary and indispensable element. The concepts of "tax literacy" and "tax culture" do not exist in our national legislation. Usually, these concepts are used on the basis of the concepts of "legal culture" or "legal literacy".

A. Spitaler followed the same position regarding the concept of "tax culture". In his works, he emphasizes that taxation depends on the economic, social, cultural, historical, geographical, psychological and other differences prevailing in individual countries and their societies [1].

A. Pausch directly connects the concept of "tax culture" with the individuals who determine the development of the tax system in the country. His concept develops the tradition of I. Schumpeter's view that: "Tax culture is an expression of human spirit and creativity" [2].

At the same time, tax literacy is a prerequisite for the formation of tax culture, and tax culture seems to be a factor that directly determines the level of development of the tax system at any stage of the social development of any country. In addition, tax culture is a necessary and important element of the tax system, which mainly determines the efficiency of its activity.

Article 51 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulates the obligation of citizens to pay taxes and local fees established by law.

An important role in the formation of the tax culture is played by the correct explanation of their constitutional duties to taxpayers and the transparent and transparent delivery of information on the calculation of taxes and fees paid by them.

The principle of voluntariness in the payment of taxes and fees will significantly increase only when the tax and fees paid to the state budget are explained to each taxpayer in the form of clear figures.

In this regard, one of the most important tasks is to ensure open and transparent information on the distribution of taxes and fees for the development of the country, improvement of the state and society, and the efficiency of reformations.

Tax culture consists of citizens understanding the importance of paying taxes for the state and society, and knowing their rights and obligations in paying them. In other words, the tax-paying state must know that tax and levy revenues are necessary to fulfill its duties.

At the current stage of development of the tax system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the tax culture in the society is at the stage of formation, because there are a number of factors that affect its development.

Firstly, the practice of providing clear figures to each taxpayer for the purposes for which taxes and fees paid to the state budget is not being implemented.

Secondly, targeted and purposeful legal promotion measures to raise the legal consciousness and legal culture of taxpayers are not being carried out sufficiently.

Thirdly, the analysis of the state and development tendency of legal relations related to taxation, the research of the current problems of taxation are being failed to be sufficiently effective.

Fourthly, joint work on explaining the rules of normative legal acts to taxpayers is not being organized together with the state tax service bodies.

Tax culture is an integral part of the general legal culture, which in turn is a component of the general culture. For example, V.M. As Sadchikov noted, “tax culture as a part of social culture includes both the legal aspect and the recognition of taxes as an integral element of the existence of society” [3].

When determining taxes, the level of tax culture of society and individuals formed by this period should be taken into account. The tax and its legal structure should not contradict the tax culture, otherwise the introduction of such a tax is accompanied by an imbalance in the interrelated parts of the tax culture: tax norms change, but the legal consciousness of individuals, which changes very slowly, values, skills and experience remain the same.

V. Nerre and A.V. Reuts say that the implementation of tax reforms can lead to the emergence of tax culture shocks and tax culture lags, which differ in the rate and depth of the imbalance in the tax culture [4]. In this place, the authors refer to fundamental changes in the tax legislation that were made quickly.

In fact, it sometimes takes a long time for taxpayers and tax authorities to adapt to new legislative innovations. Until the elements of the tax culture come into balance, the tax will not fully fulfill its fiscal and regulatory functions.

According to Maryann Richardson and Adrian Sawyer, theorists of A Taxonomy of the Tax Compliance, there are several factors that affect tax compliance, such as: age, gender, education, income level, source of income, etc. Peer-to-peer trading, decency, fairness, complexity of tax legislation, attitude of tax authorities, sanctions, and probability of inspection, tax rates, cost of tax discipline and other factors influence it [5].

It should be noted here that the concept of tax culture covers both the activities of taxpayers and the activities of tax authorities. In addition, joint consideration of this activity is required.

Tax culture is the self-expression of the state tax system and the human activity that is manifested in the forms of self-knowledge.

Tax culture is a set of stable forms of tax activity of the taxpayer, without which it cannot be restored, therefore it will not exist.

It will further increase the tax culture of taxpayers, raise the level of knowledge of taxpayers, and finally, as a result, it will serve as an incentive to voluntarily pay taxes and other mandatory payments.

The behavior of taxpayers is related to the high difficulty of fulfilling tax obligations, and therefore it is difficult to ensure active participation in the social and economic life of society. It is a very difficult task to raise the level of culture, discipline, and multifaceted requirements. For this, firstly, a well-organized service for monitoring and monitoring the fulfillment of tax obligations is necessary, that is, a highly organized system of tax administration.

The activities of tax inspections and the means of their implementation have a strong impact on the behavior of taxpayers, and they have a certain role in tax inspections. Therefore, this process is interconnected, and it seems impossible for it to exist in isolation. At the same time, it is necessary to understand that the departure of such a duty from the boundaries of general culture will inevitably lead to conflict situations.

The increasing importance of improving the tax discipline of the population requires new and modern approaches to work with taxpayers. Promotional work for tax inspectors and advisers is one of the most important directions in providing necessary information to taxpayers. This level of tax discipline can be achieved only if there is reverse connection between taxpayers and the state.

At this point, it is worth noting that it is necessary to pay special attention to the training of individuals who are entering the State Tax Service for the first time in specialized courses, to increase their fundamental knowledge such as state and legal theory, constitutional law. As a result, this allows for proper organization of tax discipline.

Today, many taxpayers turn to tax advisors to improve tax compliance. In recent years, the need for intermediaries between tax authorities and taxpayers, that is, tax advisors, can be explained by the changes in tax legislation and the adoption of new legislation in the sphere of taxes and fees, as well as the development tendency in this system.

In today's developed world, the modern market cannot be conquered by consulting services. Like many other professions, consulting emerged as a separate sphere of activity due to the general trends of the differentiation of activity and the specialization of knowledge.

One of these consulting services is tax consulting. According to the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Tax Advice", the activities of the organization of tax consultants in the provision of tax information services to physical and legal entities are subject to tax information. Tax advisers helped taxpayers to calculate and pay taxes correctly, fill out the necessary documents and optimize tax expenses, and as a result, tax discipline achieved [6-10].

The formation and development of cultural culture considered one of the criteria that shows the relationship between the state and society, which has a positive impact on the country's cultural life.

It should be noted that it couldn't be denied that ensuring tax discipline also depends on explanations by state tax authorities. However, today the explanations given by the state tax authorities regarding the application of the norms in the sphere of taxation to physical and legal entities are of a general nature, and it is clear that there is a difficulty in applying and understanding the norm. There is no explanation, but the practice of taking them from the law and giving them to the applicant without interpreting them is widespread. In another case, the explanation given by the tax authority of one state regarding the application of exactly one tax norm cannot be interpreted by the tax authority of another state.

In the tax relations that arise between tax subjects that is, taxpayers, tax agents and authorized bodies, it is necessary to pay special attention to the accuracy and fairness of tax payment, the transparency of the budget funds spent by the state. This shall create a basis for increasing the number of taxpayers who will comply with the tax legislation in the future and plan to pay tax payments on time and before time.

Based on the above, we can come to this conclusion.

Firstly, the promotion of tax culture should be aimed at the young generation and the need for taxes and it is important to form a better understanding related to the role of taxes in the formation of

the state budget, and what exactly these budget funds are spent on, as well as how important these funds are in the life of the state and society. In the list of subjects of general education schools, it is necessary to include the training course on the subjects of thermal sciences.

Secondly, the population, first of all, the youth, should be involved in carrying out targeted and targeted promotional activities to raise the tax culture, as well as to prepare a set of model documents to explain the norms and rules of normative legal acts to the population together with the state tax authorities and organization expansion.

Thirdly, preparation and distribution of informational and analytical media materials, including audio and video clips, social advertisements, reports from the scene of the incident, as well as print and electronic periodic social media materials for wide coverage of the nature and importance of the legislative documents being adopted on the subject - further development of preparation and printing of legal publications.

Fourthly, it is necessary to improve the processes of informing and advising citizens about the current tax legislation.

Fifthly, it is necessary to strengthen the right of taxpayers to get an explanation or summary of the legal consequences of these actions from the state tax service authorities before performing their actions.

In order to achieve the country's financial stability and ensure its economic security, it is necessary to improve the tax administration along with increasing the tax culture of citizens. Then high professionalism, mutual responsibility, tax culture and tax discipline can become important directions of cooperation between tax authorities and taxpayers.

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